

TEACHING MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY TO (ESP) MEDICAL STUDENTS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract. *Teaching English to med students (medical students) is a hard process for professors of English as a second or foreign language. Additionally, both professors and learners encounter significant challenges and barriers when it refers to educating and mastering medical terminology. Professors find it tough to express concepts disguised in terminology from languages other than English, including such Greek and Latin, which belong to the Indo-European and Romance linguistic groups. As a consequence, students are intimidated by extensive and sophisticated terminology and also have difficulty pronouncing, pronouncing, and comprehending foreign forms. My latest research looks into the issues that young doctors have in mastering medical terms. It supplies participants with a wide range of educational methodologies.*

Keywords: *Medical students, Indo-European and Romance linguistic groups, Greek and Latin, foreign forms, medical terms.*

INTRODUCTION

English is employed as the language of training in a wide range of occupations and services. It distinguishes from those other worldwide languages in that it openly and commonly accepts words from other languages. Many terms from Arab, Latin, Greek, French, even German, for instance, can be used not only within ordinary English but additionally in specialized areas of medicine, pharmacology, and many others. Numerous healthcare terminology, for example, have derived from the abovementioned languages, which also included Arabic, Latin, Greek, French, and German. Because English is so widely used currently, these languages really improved and were absorbed into it. As a result, English may be regarded as an overlapping language rather than a distinct language. Numerous different languages have contributed to and continue to contribute significantly to the English phenomenon. Furthermore, (Serjeantson, 1935) notes that certain terms entered English indirectly through an intervening language rather than directly through interaction with the originating language. Many of the early Italian loan phrases flow through French in this way, as do many of the earlier loan words from the east, many of which have previously passed through Greek before reaching Latin.... Words went thousands of kilometers from Asia to Europe, then from east to west and south to north through Europe, and all the way around the Mediterranean from nation to nation and generation to generation. (Talgeri, 2004) There is absolutely no wonder that English, similar to any other language, offers native speakers with such a broad range of implementations in multiple fields; even so, it is also worth mentioning that this really provides non-native English speakers with such an equally large variety of using it since it is international and can be applied to various fields of science, retail, commerce, and interaction between various nations around the world. 2005 (Abdullah) There really are three different varieties of English. English is utilized by two methods for students of English as a first language (L1), second language (SL), or foreign language (FL): English for general purposes (EGP) and English for specific purposes (ESP) (ESP). EGP supplies an infinite

number of languages that can be applied for a wide range of tasks without defining particular needs or people. Medical English is a subset of ESP that is tailored to the demands of those studying and practicing in the medical industry. The current study seeks to assess the challenges that medical students encounter while seeking to understand complex vocabulary, as well as to give tactics, procedures, and approaches for comprehending the principles concealed behind such terminology.

METHODS

The value of teaching English to healthcare learners is increasing. This is based on the fact that only the full development of competencies that ensure high-quality interaction between future doctors and their foreign colleagues in a variety of professional and academic environments is an essential aspect in the success and productivity of our future healthcare workers' job. As a consequence, working with students who learn a foreign language for specific purposes involves unique challenges. The first challenge is that planning time can be seriously constrained. Moreover, particular students' requests and needs present extra challenges for professors, which are associated with the actualization of English language in the realm of highly specialized professional communication. In this setting, the educator is regularly required to develop creative materials which are suitable for the learners' academic needs. The attraction of various authentic medical documents in English newsletters for patients, medical quizzes, multimedia materials, and leaflets in English that are distributed in medical centers in English speaking countries with the purpose of educational work among the population, in English-language medical sites, and telemedicine can help to solve such problems. All of these resources are quite valuable when developing this type of course. Furthermore, in order to completely comprehend the meaning of medical terms and concepts. Tactics, strategies, methods, and approaches are all viable options. The main focus of understanding and teaching medical terminology must be on the most important techniques and strategies. Domestic and well-known international textbooks, as well as medical faculty guides authored by domestic writers, can be used to improve educational efficacy and teach students. These resources assist students in developing a lexical and grammatical foundation, as well as skills for dealing with specific texts and knowledge of anatomy, physiology, and pathological processes. In addition, academic and professional terminology should be introduced in context. For instance, students can be taught the context of a new vocabulary unit through different texts, or they can be exposed to medical terminology and given practice using it. Exercises such as naming skeleton bones, emphasizing digestive system organs, matching terms and definitions, filling in blank phrases, and contrasting medical language with its everyday equivalents should also be used.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

In addition, each student has a distinct requirement in the classroom. As a result, the vocabulary lesson is a theme one. The majority of pupils lack motivation to study English vocabulary, and they have difficulty recalling words with similar pronunciations but different meanings. Furthermore, (August, Carlo, Dressler, and Snow, 2005) discovered that English language learners with delayed vocabulary development performed worse on grade level reading tests than their counterparts. According to (Harmer, 1992), this was considered incidental to the primary goal of language teaching, which was the development of grammatical knowledge about the language. When studying structure, terminology was essential to provide pupils with something to grasp onto, but it was rarely the major focus of learning itself. As a result, one of

the most practical and effective techniques for teaching and learning English vocabulary is to use visual aids, particularly pharmaceutical packages. Using a medicine box as a realistic teaching tool might help students concentrate on the topic, engage their attention, and broaden their understanding of global health. With the help of this medium, students can have fun, decompress, and keep their minds open to studying and practicing language.

Conclusion

Finally, the terminology represents concepts that pupils have thoroughly grasped or ideas that they may freely and actively employ when needed. Terminologies are included in students' active vocabulary because they are required for professional responsibilities as well as concept construction and formulation in a foreign language. The employment of terminologies in the professional environment of foreign language communication is determined by one's communicative competence. Terminology training in the context of a communicative approach is inextricably tied to the construction of speech patterns that mimic genuine professional activity scenarios. Based on the results of this study, we can conclude that English teachers can successfully address the issue of developing non-philological students' professional communicative competence by teaching terminology during verbal communication. Improving their capacity to hold a full-fledged professional conversation in a foreign language is one component of this.

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